

Supplementary Material

Appendix S1 – Figures and Tables

Figure S1. PAM station locations in Yushan National Park's southern sector. The map depicts the placement of 14 PAM stations (SCIH07 to SCIH20) situated along the Southern Cross-Island Highway (blue line), stretching from Meishan to Yakou.

Figure S2. Spectrograms of vocalizations from twelve target bird species. Each panel displays a spectrogram for a specific bird species and sound class: (a) Collared Owlet (song), (b) Large-billed Crow (call), (c) Taiwan Bush Warbler (song), (d) Grey-chinned Minivet (unknown), (e) Taiwan Vivid Niltava (song), (f) Eurasian Nuthatch (song), (g) Taiwan Rosefinch (call), (h) Taiwan Yuhina (song), (i) Taiwan Shortwing (song), (j) Ashy Wood-Pigeon (song), (k) Green-backed Tit (song), and (l) Gray-headed Woodpecker (song).

Figure S3. Illustration of Intersection Ratio (IR) calculation. A small bounding box (S, green) overlaps with a big one (blue) and forms an intersection area (I, yellow). The value of IR (i.e., Intersection Ratio of the smaller object) equals the area of I divided by the area of S. When the value of IRs is greater than 0.25, the two boxes are merged into a new box which is the smallest convex hull (red) of the two original boxes.

Figure S4. Illustration of Intersection over Union (IoU) calculation. Two bounding boxes (green and blue rectangles) overlap with each other and form an intersection area (I, yellow) and a union area (U, grey and yellow). The value of IoU (i.e., Intersection over Union) equals the area of I divided by the area of U. When the value of IoU is greater than 0.1, the two boxes are merged into a new box which is the smallest convex hull (red) of the two original boxes.

Figure S5. Precision and recall metrics for twelve target bird species. Each panel displays the precision (blue lines) and recall (orange lines) values for a specific bird species: (a) Collared Owlet, (b) Large-billed Crow, (c) Taiwan Bush Warbler, (d) Grey-chinned Minivet, (e) Taiwan Vivid Niltava, (f) Eurasian Nuthatch, (g) Taiwan Rosefinch, (h) Taiwan Yuhina, (i) Taiwan Shortwing, (j) Ashy Wood-Pigeon, (k) Green-backed Tit, and (l) Gray-headed Woodpecker.

Figure S6. Variation in daily vocal activity for twelve target bird species. Each panel portrays the predicted daily vocal activity rate (VAR_d, vocalizations per day) against the Day of the Year (DOY) as predicted by the comprehensive GAM for a specific species: (a) Collared Owlet, (b) Large-billed Crow, (c) Taiwan Bush Warbler, (d) Grey-chinned Minivet, (e) Taiwan Vivid Niltava, (f) Eurasian Nuthatch, (g) Taiwan Rosefinch, (h) Taiwan Yuhina, (i) Taiwan Shortwing, (j) Ashy Wood-Pigeon, (k) Green-backed Tit, and (l) Gray-headed Woodpecker. The fitted lines depict the best (i.e. full) GAM with a 95% confidence interval (dashed grey lines). The x-axis spans DOY values from 60 (March 1) to 180 (June 29) for 2021. The y-axis shows the smoothed effects of DOY for each species. Horizontal red dashed lines indicate baseline levels. Accompanying each plot are the estimated degrees of freedom (edf) and significance codes (***) $p < 0.001$, (**) $p < 0.01$, (*) $p < 0.05$.

Figure S7. Altitudinal variation in daily vocal activity for twelve target bird species. Each panel displays the predicted daily vocal activity rate (VAR_d, vocalizations per day) in relation to altitude, as predicted by the comprehensive GAM for a specific species: (a) Collared Owlet, (b) Large-billed Crow, (c) Taiwan Bush Warbler, (d) Grey-chinned Minivet, (e) Taiwan Vivid Niltava, (f) Eurasian Nuthatch, (g) Taiwan Rosefinch, (h) Taiwan Yuhina, (i) Taiwan Shortwing, (j) Ashy Wood-Pigeon, (k) Green-backed Tit, and (l) Gray-headed Woodpecker. The fitted lines indicate the best (i.e. full) GAM with a 95% confidence interval (dashed grey lines). The x-axis represents altitude values in meters above sea level (m a.s.l.). The y-axis shows the smoothed effects of altitude for each species. Horizontal red dashed lines indicate baseline levels. Alongside each plot are the estimated degrees of freedom (edf) and significance codes (***) $p < 0.001$, (**) $p < 0.01$, (*) $p < 0.05$.

Figure S8. Environmental influences on daily vocal activity rate. Each panel illustrates the predicted relationship between the daily vocal activity rate (VAR_d, vocalizations per day) and a specific environmental predictor: (a) Corrected Precipitation (Rainfall, in mm), (b) Wind Speed at 2 meters (WindSpeed, in m/s), (c) Temperature at 2 meters (Temp, in °C), (d) Relative Humidity at 2 meters (RH, presented as a percentage), and (e) Surface Pressure (SP, in kPa). The fitted curves are based on the best (i.e. full) GAM with a 95% confidence interval (dashed grey lines). The x-axis spans the range of values for each environmental variable, while the y-axis depicts the smoothed effects of these predictors on VAR_d. Horizontal red dashed lines indicate the baseline level. Each plot is annotated with the estimated degrees of freedom (edf) and significance codes (***) $p < 0.001$, (**) $p < 0.01$, (*) $p < 0.05$.

Figure S9. Short-term periodic representation of vocal activity clusters and rainfall. The numbers at the bottom represent the Day of Year (DOY). Above these numbers are rectangles colored and numbered to indicate different clustering results: 1 (red), 2 (orange), 3 (blue), 4 (green), and 5 (yellow). Above the clusters are the months, and the line graph represents rainfall (in mm) from the SCIH13 PAM station.

Table S1: PAM stations: locations and vegetation types. This table provides the locations and associated vegetation types for the 14 PAM stations.

Station	Longitude (°E)	Latitude (°N)	Elevation (m.a.s.l.)	Vegetation Types*
SCIH07	120.858	23.288	1500	Submontane evergreen broad-leaved forest
SCIH08	120.864	23.282	1600	
SCIH09	120.874	23.280	1700	Montane evergreen broad-leaved forest
SCIH10	120.885	23.284	1800	
SCIH11	120.893	23.278	1900	
SCIH12	120.900	23.285	2000	
SCIH13	120.908	23.278	2100	
SCIH14	120.918	23.284	2200	Montane mixed coniferous broadleaved forest
SCIH15	120.915	23.272	2300	
SCIH16	120.918	23.261	2400	Upper montane coniferous forest
SCIH17	120.935	23.257	2500	
SCIH18	120.940	23.266	2600	
SCIH19	120.947	23.260	2700	
SCIH20	120.955	23.268	2800	

* Minister of the Interior. (2022). The 4th Overall Review of Yushan National Park Plan. Minister of the Interior.

Table S2. Vocalizations detected in Yushan National Park, March to June, 2021. This table enumerates the total vocalizations detected by SILIC from audio recordings gathered at 12 PAM stations within Yushan National Park during the specified period.

Species	SCIH07	SCIH08	SCIH09	SCIH10	SCIH12	SCIH13	SCIH14	SCIH15	SCIH16	SCIH17	SCIH19	SCIH20	Total
Collared Owlet	3448	12926	13193	32356	8508	8894	5352	7924	1388	4734	3908	861	103492
Large-billed Crow	12042	10348	26091	15415	29960	99693	86504	257751	21596	42139	31146	58267	690952
Taiwan Bush Warbler	226	612	336	253	18530	770	887	1769	134238	1121	517927	249620	926289
Grey-chinned Minivet	184460	98768	191994	80334	193273	60522	70205	68979	111460	63451	10625	11853	1145924
Taiwan Vivid Niltava	68691	80073	94494	95357	219716	47207	111494	206494	32270	41752	21238	10966	1029752
Eurasian Nuthatch	317	3830	6737	953	5472	1124	1330	7457	1752	1037	9255	9140	48404
Taiwan Rosefinch	3408	3017	1945	1847	20799	2685	10659	5573	9990	6874	36311	97614	200722
Taiwan Yuhina	118258	75187	127814	117081	139849	234402	228418	263998	418919	481602	331056	327254	2863838
Taiwan Shortwing	592	2132	192	758	954	5911	191606	767	119523	42184	186762	51590	602971
Ashy Wood-Pigeon	958	10738	3108	11318	2810	7784	1544	8056	1040	7140	8016	569	63081
Green-backed Tit	36379	25787	61296	19021	79901	33335	68855	44376	43636	42478	30627	18303	503994
Gray-headed Woodpecker	232	534	1559	989	492	1122	2975	4378	1800	3908	3082	2241	23312
Total	429011	323952	528759	375682	720264	503449	779829	877522	897612	738420	1189953	838278	8202731

Table S3. Traits and model performance metrics for twelve target species. This table details the traits of the 12 target species, provides information on the test dataset, and presents associated model performance metrics.

Species	Guild*	Elevation Boundary**		Test Sample Size		Model Performance Metrics***				
		(m.a.s.l.)		(sample)		Threshold	Precision	Recall	AUC	AP
		Lower	Upper	Positive	Negative					
Collared Owlet (<i>Taenioptynx brodiei</i>)	Raptorial Carnivores (RC)	213	2458	30	70	0.33	0.95	0.83	0.99	0.97
Large-billed Crow (<i>Corvus macrorhynchos</i>)	Ground Omnivores (GO)	18	2989	42	58	0.35	0.95	0.78	0.95	0.94
Taiwan Bush Warbler (<i>Locustella alishanensis</i>)	Bush Insectivores (BI)	639	3269	32	68	0.48	0.95	0.73	0.92	0.9
Grey-chinned Minivet (<i>Pericrocotus solaris</i>)	Tree Hovers (TH)	68	2273	58	42	0.13	0.95	0.97	0.99	0.99
Taiwan Vivid Niltava (<i>Niltava vivida</i>)	Air Flycatchers (AF)	206	2609	25	75	0.43	0.95	0.88	0.97	0.95
Eurasian Nuthatch (<i>Sitta europaea</i>)	Bole Gleaners (BG)	835	3133	26	74	0.51	0.95	0.67	0.89	0.85
Taiwan Rosefinch (<i>Carpodacus formosanus</i>)	Ground Graminivores (GG)	1723	3626	55	45	0.23	0.97	1.00	1.00	1.00
Taiwan Yuhina (<i>Yuhina brunneiceps</i>)	Tree Omnivores (TO)	354	2746	26	74	0.74	0.95	0.65	0.98	0.88
Taiwan Shortwing (<i>Brachypteryx goodfellowi</i>)	Ground Insectivores (GI)	1137	2989	49	51	0.65	0.95	0.57	0.95	0.95
Ashy Wood-Pigeon (<i>Columba pulchricollis</i>)	Tree Fruitivore (TF)	92	2618	38	62	0.43	0.95	0.61	0.87	0.87
Green-backed Tit (<i>Parus monticolus</i>)	Tree Insectivores (TI)	354	2618	26	74	0.37	0.95	0.65	0.95	0.9
Gray-headed Woodpecker (<i>Picus canus</i>)	Bole Peckers (BP)	675	3050	17	83	0.72	0.95	0.35	0.98	0.9

* Ding, T. S. (1993). Avian community ecology of mature forests in Mt. Yushan [Master Thesis]. National Taiwan University.

** Tsai, P. Y., Ko, C. J., Hsieh, C., Su, Y. T., Lu, Y. J., Lin, R. S., & Tuanmu, M. N. (2020). A trait dataset for Taiwan's breeding birds. Biodiversity Data Journal, 8, e49735. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.8.e49735>

*** The performance metric of the model is calculated based on a threshold where the precision is no less than 0.95.

Table S4. Best-fit Generalized Additive Model (GAM) for predicting daily vocal activity rate. This table displays the results of the GAM that predicts daily vocal activity rate (vocalizations per day) based on interactions between Species and Vegetation types. The model incorporates smoothed effects of Altitude (meters, varying by Species), corrected precipitation (Rainfall, mm), wind speed at 2 meters (WindSpeed, m/s), temperature at 2 meters (Temp, °C), relative humidity at 2 meters (RH, %), surface pressure (SP, kPa), and Day of the Year (DOY, varying by Species). Presented are the Estimated Coefficients (EC) along with standard errors (SE), Z-scores, and p-values. Weather data were sourced from the NASA/POWER CERES/MERRA2 Native Resolution Daily Data repository, accessible at <https://power.larc.nasa.gov/data-access-viewer/>. Vegetation data were provided by the Minister of the Interior (2022).

Coefficient	EC	SE	Z	p
(Intercept)	7.88	0.22	35.69	<0.001 ***
Species				
Collared Owlet	-7.74	0.34	-23.05	<0.001 ***
Large-billed Crow	-4.93	0.32	-15.60	<0.001 ***
Taiwan Bush Warbler	2.26	0.55	4.12	<0.001 ***
Grey-chinned Minivet	-0.01	0.33	-0.03	0.978
Taiwan Vivid Niltava	-2.26	0.33	-6.84	<0.001 ***
Eurasian Nuthatch	-5.39	0.38	-14.00	<0.001 ***
Taiwan Rosefinch	-1.53	0.34	-4.46	<0.001 ***
Taiwan Yuhina	4.54	0.41	11.09	<0.001 ***
Taiwan Shortwing	-8.59	0.34	-24.93	<0.001 ***
Ashy Wood-Pigeon	-0.67	0.33	-2.04	0.041 *
Gray-headed Woodpecker	-5.70	0.32	-17.97	<0.001 ***
Vegetation types				
Montane mixed coniferous broadleaved forest	-0.58	0.25	-2.28	0.023 *
Montane evergreen broad-leaved forest	-0.66	0.36	-1.82	0.069
Submontane evergreen broad-leaved forest	-1.53	0.44	-3.47	<0.001 ***
Species : Vegetation types				
Collared Owlet : Montane mixed coniferous broadleaved forest	3.83	0.49	7.80	<0.001 ***
Large-billed Crow : Montane mixed coniferous broadleaved forest	3.98	0.37	10.65	<0.001 ***
Taiwan Bush Warbler : Montane mixed coniferous broadleaved forest	-8.00	2.01	-3.99	<0.001 ***
Grey-chinned Minivet : Montane mixed coniferous broadleaved forest	-0.22	0.51	-0.42	0.672
Taiwan Vivid Niltava : Montane mixed coniferous broadleaved forest	2.79	0.51	5.45	<0.001 ***
Eurasian Nuthatch : Montane mixed coniferous broadleaved forest	2.37	0.96	2.46	0.014 *
Taiwan Rosefinch : Montane mixed coniferous broadleaved forest	-0.70	0.64	-1.11	0.268

Taiwan Yuhina : Montane mixed coniferous broadleaved forest	-8.99	1.17	-7.68	<0.001 ***
Taiwan Shortwing : Montane mixed coniferous broadleaved forest	3.99	0.59	6.73	<0.001 ***
Ashy Wood-Pigeon : Montane mixed coniferous broadleaved forest	0.36	0.50	0.72	0.472
Gray-headed Woodpecker : Montane mixed coniferous broadleaved forest	1.50	0.35	4.22	<0.001 ***
Collared Owlet : Montane evergreen broad-leaved forest	5.52	0.54	10.24	<0.001 ***
Large-billed Crow : Montane evergreen broad-leaved forest	5.29	0.52	10.18	<0.001 ***
Taiwan Bush Warbler : Montane evergreen broad-leaved forest	-10.08	0.56	-18.09	<0.001 ***
Grey-chinned Minivet : Montane evergreen broad-leaved forest	-1.51	0.53	-2.85	0.004 **
Taiwan Vivid Niltava : Montane evergreen broad-leaved forest	1.19	0.53	2.25	0.024 *
Eurasian Nuthatch : Montane evergreen broad-leaved forest	1.37	0.55	2.51	0.012 *
Taiwan Rosefinch : Montane evergreen broad-leaved forest	-3.56	0.53	-6.67	<0.001 ***
Taiwan Yuhina : Montane evergreen broad-leaved forest	-14.56	0.54	-26.94	<0.001 ***
Taiwan Shortwing : Montane evergreen broad-leaved forest	6.30	0.54	11.66	<0.001 ***
Ashy Wood-Pigeon : Montane evergreen broad-leaved forest	-1.84	0.53	-3.48	<0.001 ***
Gray-headed Woodpecker : Montane evergreen broad-leaved forest	0.34	0.53	0.64	0.523
Collared Owlet : Submontane evergreen broad-leaved forest	7.34	0.67	10.94	<0.001 ***
Large-billed Crow : Submontane evergreen broad-leaved forest	5.30	0.63	8.37	<0.001 ***
Taiwan Bush Warbler : Submontane evergreen broad-leaved forest	-9.41	1.08	-8.74	<0.001 ***
Grey-chinned Minivet : Submontane evergreen broad-leaved forest	-2.59	0.67	-3.89	<0.001 ***
Taiwan Vivid Niltava : Submontane evergreen broad-leaved forest	1.82	0.67	2.74	0.006 **
Eurasian Nuthatch : Submontane evergreen broad-leaved forest	0.00	0.77	0.00	1.000
Taiwan Rosefinch : Submontane evergreen broad-leaved forest	-2.60	0.69	-3.75	<0.001 ***
Taiwan Yuhina : Submontane evergreen broad-leaved forest	-8.94	0.82	-10.87	<0.001 ***
Taiwan Shortwing : Submontane evergreen broad-leaved forest	9.70	0.69	14.06	<0.001 ***
Ashy Wood-Pigeon : Submontane evergreen broad-leaved forest	-2.84	0.66	-4.28	<0.001 ***
Gray-headed Woodpecker : Submontane evergreen broad-leaved forest	0.35	0.64	0.56	0.578

Smooth terms				
s(DOY) : Species	edf	Ref.df	Chi.sq	p-value
s(DOY) : Collared Owlet	7.01	8.074	896.38	<0.001 ***
s(DOY) : Large-billed Crow	5.207	6.321	78.22	<0.001 ***
s(DOY) : Taiwan Bush Warbler	8.522	8.932	281.4	<0.001 ***
s(DOY) : Grey-chinned Minivet	4.336	5.336	74.48	<0.001 ***
s(DOY) : Taiwan Vivid Niltava	8.319	8.867	269.35	<0.001 ***
s(DOY) : Eurasian Nuthatch	7.181	8.208	459.03	<0.001 ***
s(DOY) : Taiwan Rosefinch	7.227	8.242	117.13	<0.001 ***
s(DOY) : Taiwan Yuhina	7.636	8.525	160.26	<0.001 ***
s(DOY) : Taiwan Shortwing	8.073	8.765	453.26	<0.001 ***
s(DOY) : Ashy Wood-Pigeon	6.303	7.45	235.75	<0.001 ***

s(DOY) : Gray-headed Woodpecker	8.288	8.856	664.04	<0.001 ***
s(DOY) : Taiwan Yuhina	4.381	5.388	189.82	<0.001 ***
s(Altitude) : Species				
s(Altitude) : Collared Owllet	7.66	7.939	314.23	<0.001 ***
s(Altitude) : Large-billed Crow	6.762	7.53	286.36	<0.001 ***
s(Altitude) : Taiwan Bush Warbler	7.988	7.999	2132.01	<0.001 ***
s(Altitude) : Grey-chinned Minivet	7.731	7.956	162.41	<0.001 ***
s(Altitude) : Taiwan Vivid Niltava	7.732	7.956	100.66	<0.001 ***
s(Altitude) : Eurasian Nuthatch	7.946	7.994	719.93	<0.001 ***
s(Altitude) : Taiwan Rosefinch	7.858	7.981	400.91	<0.001 ***
s(Altitude) : Taiwan Yuhina	7.965	7.997	2070.66	<0.001 ***
s(Altitude) : Taiwan Shortwing	7.82	7.975	595.84	<0.001 ***
s(Altitude) : Ashy Wood-Pigeon	7.701	7.948	104.2	<0.001 ***
s(Altitude) : Gray-headed Woodpecker	5.678	6.72	66.89	<0.001 ***
s(Altitude) : Taiwan Yuhina	6.307	7.216	50.05	<0.001 ***
s(Rainfall)	7.171	8.001	75.95	<0.001 ***
s(WindSpeed)	8.011	8.691	82.83	<0.001 ***
s(Temp)	6.855	7.936	174.52	<0.001 ***
s(RH)	6.447	7.555	38.08	<0.001 ***
s(SP)	6.886	7.898	61.59	<0.001 ***

Significant codes: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$

Appendix S2 – Performance metrics

For performance evaluation, we applied the trained model on an unseen test dataset and got the predicted class of each data. The predicted results were compared with the ground truth to get confusion matrix that indicates four parameters as true positive (TP), true negative (TN), false positive (FP) and false negative (FN) (Fig. S7). Then, we can calculate the performance metrics as precision (Eq. 1) and recall (Eq. 2).

$$\text{Eq. 1} \quad \text{Precision} = \frac{\text{TP}}{(\text{TP}+\text{FP})}$$

$$\text{Eq. 2} \quad \text{Recall} = \frac{\text{TP}}{(\text{TP}+\text{FN})}$$

		Predicted Class	
		Positive	Negative
Ground Truth	Positive	True Positive (TP)	False Negative (FN)
	Negative	False Positive (FP)	True Negative (TN)

Figure S7. Confusion matrix

Precision-recall curve (PR curve) and average precision (AP)

For each class, when different threshold score is selected, different values of parameters will be calculated. A PR curve (precision-recall curve) is so plotted with precision (y-axis) and recall (x-axis) along with the changes in threshold score. The entire area underneath the PR curve can be measured and named average precision (AP) (Fig. S8).

Figure S8. Precision-recall curve (PR curve) and average precision (AP)

ROC curve and AUC (Area Under the ROC Curve)

The same as PR curve, an ROC curve (receiver operating characteristic curve) is plotted with true positive rate (TPR or recall, y-axis) against the false positive rate (FPR, x-axis, Eq. 3). The entire area under the ROC curve is AUC and the average value of AUC of all classes is macro-average AUC (Fig. S9).

$$\text{Eq. 3} \quad \text{FPR} = \frac{\text{FP}}{(\text{FP} + \text{TN})}$$

Figure S9. ROC curve and AUC (Area Under the ROC Curve)